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LG/LID: 468 Dolakha Newar
SOURCE(S): Genetti, Carol. 1994. A descriptive and historical account of the Dolakha Newari Dialect
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Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc.)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries

As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially is the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit.

If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.

Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")

Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.

Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

--occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions
labials almost never word-final, but frequent in medial coda
r (approximant) never word-initial (allophone retroflex ɖ instead), but common syll-init in medial (also in all final positions)
aspirated obstruents never in final (syllable & word)
but asp okay in all onset positions

--voicing, aspiration patterns

--manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)

--place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)

-- gemination
geminate C's are rare--they only occur syllable init in word-medial, and only obstruent geminates. ha.tti 'elephant'

--vowel height/backness (quality)

--nasal vowels (see "rules")

-- vowel length

--VV sequences (includes diphthongs)
diphthongs within same syllable always of 2 vowel qualities
VV-sequences otherwise are bimorphemic: CV-V, where CV is verb stem and -V is an inflectional suffix. Never results in single, long V: . Genetti says there are 2 distinct pulses and a noticeable pitch drop on the 2nd V.
 1 suffix looks like a diphthong (-eu '3sgFUT'). Seems to be monosyllabic. Otherwise, all cases of diphthongs seem to occur in roots.

--idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

--vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

1 case Vowel Harmony; domain is prefix and verb root. Doesn't seem to include suffixes. Happens with all of the 3 prefixes (NEG, HORT, PROHIB). More restricted in some speakers than others.

All prefixes are monosyll with a vowel a (open front). The vowel quality changes to either aa (open back) or o (close-mid back) depending on the vowel in the root (aa or o).

Note that vowel harmony is BLOCKED if the verb root begins with Cy.

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a

phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

(C)(C)V(V)(C)

but as mentioned, V-only words are very rare.

No coda C clusters anywhere

onset clusters permitted in all places, but medial onset clusters more restricted (e.g. no Cy in medial)

--C COMBOS—are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

**Cy (pal. glide) in medial onset position, but frequent word-initially*

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)

A couple of examples, some monomorph, some bi-morph where suffix/enclitic is C-only: jhark 'harass'

kaen 'son=ERG' (kae=n) (ae = single complex syllabic nuclei). No mention of n being syllabic--discussed as n-only if following a vowel, na if following a C. Suggests that it syllabifies as coda if following a vowel.

bijain 'grandfather=ERG' (bijai=n)

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

On disyllabics, single primary stress on initial syllable (not sure if this pertains to prefixes too)

On polysyllabics also a secondary stress on 3rd syllable.

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed

above)?

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units

No tone, no pitch accent

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included.

What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

Words may never be V-only (1 or 2 single exceptions, like proximal demonstrative u 'this')

Okay for words to be vowel-initial.

Verbs are minimally VC in size

other parts of speech CV minimal

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/ complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different *types* of reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

Genetti describes a rare process of verb duplication, but it is not exactly the same thing. Transcribes as 2 words. Typically happens in emphatic situations, and first instance of verb followed by an emphatic particle and the 2nd instance takes TAM.

Do tuŋ mo-Doŋ-gi

stand EMPH NEG-stand-1PST

'I couldn't even stand at all'

So it looks like total redup of verb root, but there's also this intervening emphatic particle.

Hardly ever happens.

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated). Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)

Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bɪ] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

No discussion or examples of compounds

Maybe this is a language without productive compounding?

Only a few examples of V + V concatenation, in complementation constructions.

complements of cognition verbs:

<i>ji</i>	<i>ktm</i>	<i>u-i=uri</i>	<i>kha</i>	<i>jana</i>	<i>maa=n</i>
<i>1sg</i>	<i>KTM</i>	<i>go-INF=EMPH</i>	<i>talk</i>	<i>1.GEN</i>	<i>mother=ERG</i>

paatalyaa _____ *yet-cu*
discover *do-3PST*

'My mother found out about my plans to go to KTM'

In these cases, the 2 verbs are treated as 2 pwords.

In other clause combining strategies, the (first) non-finite verb takes some kind of participial suffix.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.